

**Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe
Phase 3**

**Prototype of the data layout concepts developed and
demonstrated in a first implementation
Milestone M3.4**

ESiWACE3 Milestone M3.4

EuroHPC
Joint Undertaking

Funded by the European Union. This work has received funding from the European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (JU) under grant agreement No 101093054.

Co-funded by
the European Union

Contact details

Project Office: esiwace3@bsc.es

Website: www.esiwace.eu

X: <https://X.com/esiwace>

YouTube: <https://www.youtube.com/@esiwace880>

LinkedIn: linkedin.com/company/esiwace3/

ESiWACE is on Zenodo, the Open Access repository for scientific results
<https://zenodo.org/communities/esiwace>

ESiWACE3 Milestone M3.4

Disclaimer: Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (JU). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

ESiWACE3 Milestone M3.4

Lead Beneficiary:

Deutsches Klimarechenzentrum GmbH (DKRZ), Karsten Peters-von Gehlen

Other contributing authors:

Max-Planck-Gesellschaft Zur Forderung Der Wissenschaften EV (MPI-M), Jairo Segura

Type:

See the original description in the [Grant Agreement](#)

Dissemination level:

See the original description in the [Grant Agreement](#)

Delivery date:

30 June 2025 (M30)

Means of verifications:

Software tests run successfully for most important use cases as to be defined in D3.1

Achieved:

Yes

If not achieved, indicate forecast achievement date:

n/a

Comments:

n/a

Prototype of the data layout concepts developed and demonstrated in a first implementation

Different data layout concepts have been developed especially in the frameworks of other EU-funded projects like NextGEMS, EERIE or Destination Earth. Each of these projects favours a different data layout and data serving concept (see Deliverable D3.1 for more details). None of these data layout concepts have achieved full operational status, hence they are prototypical. This is especially the case since the performance of each of these data layout and data serving concepts has not yet been thoroughly evaluated in comparison to the others given specific use cases.

Each of the data layout concepts is a joint development of ESiWACE3 partners (MPIM, DKRZ, ECMWF), albeit not specifically funded by ESiWACE3. Therefore, the goal of the work done in Task 3.1 is to perform a thorough evaluation of the prototypes in order to further optimize data layout concepts over the rest of the ESiWACE3 project and then provide well informed recommendations to the scientific community focusing on advancing towards exascale weather- and climate modelling applications.

Here, use cases used for data layout evaluation are defined as specific data analysis procedures deemed typical for a scientific workflow. These use cases are described in more detail in D3.1 and their implementation for evaluation purposes is available via GitLab:

https://gitlab.dkrz.de/m300913/ESW3_D3.1

The above code includes timings for data access and analysis to allow preliminary benchmarking. It must be noted though, that every prototypical data layout is available for a specific dataset. In other words, we do not have all prototypical data layouts available for a single dataset. Therefore, the comparison of the data layout performance does not represent a true benchmark. The tests do however give a good estimate of the data layout suitability for each analysis use case and are therefore very valuable (because no evaluation exists so far).

Most analysis use cases (as defined in D3.1) have been implemented and run on the DKRZ supercomputer infrastructure. See project deliverable D3.1 for detailed results.